

Keywords:

#marketplace, #service, #workflow, #resource, #researcher, #portal, #catalogue, #socialscience, #EOSCinPractice, #humanities, #discovery

Developing an interoperable central hub for Social Sciences and Humanities resources.

An EOSC in Practice Story on the SSH Open Marketplace.

The project involved

SSHOC (Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud) is a project funded by the EU framework programme Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement

no. 823782, running from January 2019 to April 2022. It united **53 organisations** in developing the social sciences and humanities area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

"Through the SSH Open Marketplace we are opening a bit the black box of digital methods to a wide range of research communities and the society in general, overcoming the fragmentation of resources characterising the social sciences and humanities"

Laure Barbot, DARIAH Project Officer

The Users

The users in this EOSC in Practice story are **Social Science and Humanities (SSH) researchers** and **data experts** that need to find relevant resources and digital methods used in their specific research fields. In addition, the service described here can be also useful for **research institutions** and **policy makers** to have an overview of the tooling, service and resource landscapes in social sciences and humanities.

The Challenge

The Social Sciences and Humanities communities needed a central point to **gather and exchange information** about their tools, services, and datasets. Although plenty of project websites, service registries, and data repositories existed, they were mostly fragmented. The lack of contextualisation connecting these assets and offering domain-relevant means to discuss and enrich them was evident. Also, there was a need to **digitalise** this research domain which, in most cases, was not yet digital native. This siloed environment was the challenge SSHOC set out to bridge in January 2019.

The solution

The **SSH Open Marketplace, delivered in 2022**, is a discovery platform supporting researchers in the multi-faceted domain of humanities and social sciences at every step of the research data lifecycle. By grouping and connecting a wide set of tools, services, databases, training materials, workflows and publications on social sciences and humanities, the marketplace helps SSH academics and researchers to address their research questions providing these resources as "contextualised solutions".

Preview of SSHOC Open Marketplace Service Catalogue

In addition, the marketplace works also as a community-gathering platform where all SSH researchers can contribute to the content, exchange information and feed on their experiences.

The service provider

The **SSH Open Marketplace** was developed in the SSHOC project. In particular, **DARIAH ERIC** coordinated the work for the creation of the marketplace, **CLARIN ERIC** took care of the interoperability aspects, and SSHOC Coordinator **CESSDA ERIC** supported the onboarding on the EOSC Portal. These three ERICs are maintaining the service relying on two main service providers: the **Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH)** of the Austrian Academy of Sciences and the **Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC)** affiliated to the Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry of the Polish Academy of Sciences.

The development of this marketplace is a true collaborative and community effort where also the users have a significant role. By contributing to the tools and various resources offered in the portal, the users play a major role in ensuring the quality and continuous curation of this discovery portal.

Why do I need EOSC?

Providing this tool on the EOSC portal, allows to:

- » reach a wider audience
- » help researchers, as community contributors to the SSH Open Marketplace, make their research more visible across Europe
- » collect feedback on the offered service
- » upgrade the service level offered to users thanks to the services available for EOSC Providers

Moreover, the SSH Open Marketplace harvests SSH resources from the EOSC portal to provide SSH researchers with easy access to all available tools in their domain. That way, the users of the SSH Open Marketplace benefit from an easy to use hub and from updated information on how to use new resources, e.g. via the available workflows, which help researchers learn about new tools and save time to perform their research tasks.

The **SSH Open Marketplace** is available on the [EOSC Portal](#), explore this resource!

What the users of the service say

"The SSH Open Marketplace is useful for the whole Social Sciences and Humanities community! The easier it is to browse information about existing resources, the better it is for everyone. It saves time and enables research. Curation of metadata in discovery portals matter and past experience has shown that it is difficult! The collaborative approach of the SSH Open Marketplace where anyone can contribute in enriching the records while browsing the catalogue and where a team of moderators supports its continuous curation, is an interesting way to overcome some of these challenges."

Amelia Sanz, María Robles and Adrián Menéndez de la Cuesta from Complutense University of Madrid.

The impact on society

The **SSH Open Marketplace** helps enriching the EOSC ecosystem with new resources from the social sciences and humanities domain. Being an open access platform, it allows anyone to browse, discover or contribute to the resources thus helping to open the "black box" of digital methods to the wider public. It provides insights that can be useful for a wide array of stakeholders including companies and SMEs who are working to provide services for researchers. On the one side, they can do a gap analysis on what is missing to improve their offering by looking at the resources already available in the Marketplace; on the other side, they can use the Marketplace to promote their services.

Across disciplines

The SSHOC project successfully bridged the silos between the SSH ESFRIs and research communities, during the 40-month lifetime of the project. Moreover, thanks to specific methodological resources such as the workflows, it is also possible to benefit from a stronger degree of cross-disciplinarity when, for instance, a method deriving from the physics domain is used in social science research to analyse specific types of data. The marketplace allows this kind of connections. Some examples on cross-disciplinary opportunities are also provided by the [science projects](#) led by SSHOC within EOSC Future.

Future developments

The SSH Open Marketplace will be upscaled to better tackle the challenge of multilinguality. Also, better connections with other services from the SSH Open Cluster or beyond, such as the Language Resource Switchboard, the Virtual Collection Registry or the GoTriple platform, are also foreseen.

Sustainability for an EOSC in practice

Three ERICs are committed to sustaining this platform financially under the [SSH Open Cluster](#), an instrument of further collaboration between different SSH community stakeholders taking an active role in promoting the quality and impact of SSH within the European Research Area and beyond.

Future funding model scenarios

Three ERICs, DARIAH, CLARIN and CESSDA, are committed to sustain the platform until the end of 2023. The sustainability activities include an Editorial Board taking care of the platform curation and moderation, as well as participation in events where the use of the platform is promoted to interested stakeholders. The objective is to further extend the agreement under the SSH Open Cluster Memorandum of Understanding, to enhance mutual interaction, build upon and expand existing synergies and expertise, and support sharing of know-how in all areas of common interest. A sustainability plan has been developed in this regard and is available [here](#).

Useful material related to this story

- » [SSHOC Service Catalogue](#)
- » [SSH Open Marketplace](#)
- » [Training Material](#)
- » [SSHOC Zenodo Collection](#)
- » [Who needs directories: a dh 2020 forum proposal](#)

Want to learn more about the other services being developed by SSHOC? Read [here](#).

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